

THE APPLICATION OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES TO TEACH LATIN LANGUAGE

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Аннотация: Цель данной статьи - проанализировать некоторые современные педагогические технологии, которые применялись на занятиях по латинскому языку. В связи с внедрением компьютерных технологий в процессе обучения данная тема является актуальной и востребованной. Применение интерактивных методов обучения - один из значимых вопросов методики преподавания. В статье были детально рассмотрены метод «круглого стола» и метод «портфолио», которые активно использовались при изучении дисциплины «Латинский язык и медицинская терминология» в медицинских ВУЗах. Приведены примеры применения данных технологий в условиях образовательного процесса на занятиях по латинскому языку. В ходе использования данных методик выявлено несколько полезных моментов.

Ключевые слова: педагогические методики, метод «круглого стола», метод «портфолио», дисциплина «Латинский язык».

Abstract: The purpose of this article is to analyze some modern pedagogical technologies that were used in Latin classes. In connection with the introduction of computer technology in the learning process, this topic is relevant and in demand. The use of interactive teaching methods is one of the important issues of teaching methods. The article describes the method of "round table" and the method of "portfolio", which are actively used in the study of the discipline "Latin language" at the faculty of clinical psychology and medical-prophylactic faculty of Ryazan State Medical University named after academician I.P.Pavlov. Examples of

application of these technologies in the educational process in the classroom in Latin are given.

Keywords: pedagogical methods, the method of "round table", the method of "portfolio", Latin language course.

Pedagogical science is in constant development. New directions and methods are emerging aimed at achieving the main goal - education and training of the individual. In modern methodological literature, the concept of “pedagogical technologies” is becoming more relevant. So, there are many definitions of this term. For example, V.P. Bespalko wrote the following: “Pedagogical technologies are a set of means and methods for reproducing theoretically based processes of teaching and upbringing, allowing the successful implementation of educational goals.” B.T. Likhachev believed that this is “a set of psychological and pedagogical attitudes that determine a special set and arrangement of forms, methods, teaching techniques, educational means; it is a toolkit of the pedagogical process, which is implemented in the technological process.

The various types of educational work in classes at medical universities contribute to mastering the culture of thinking, the ability to logically correctly formulate its results in written and oral speech. The importance of intensifying the cognitive activity of students is emphasized in the article by Motorina I.V., Motorina A.V. Expanding students' opportunities to shape their cognitive activity and increase the intensity of the educational process in this field of education, it is recommended to use various forms and methods of teaching. This article discusses in detail interactive methods such as round tables and portfolios. These methods are widely used in the study of 'Latin' in the departments of Russian and Latin languages. In addition to written or oral frontal questioning, pedagogical dictation and work with tables, our department uses the “round table” method to consolidate the studied content. This method involves holding educational discussions with the aim of repeating the studied theoretical, lexical and grammatical material before the final or final certification. The main goal of such classes is to provide students with the

opportunity to use the acquired theoretical knowledge in practice. Participants must learn to act as speakers and opponents, develop skills and abilities to pose and solve intellectual problems and questions, defend their arguments and demonstrate achievements in theoretical and practical training. At practical round table sessions, the main topics of the course and the most difficult issues to understand and master are discussed. Topics are discussed in plenary sessions, which ensures the active participation of each student. Preparation and discussion of topics discussed at round tables solves a number of pedagogical problems. Of particular importance is the creation of conditions for independent study of medical terminology, motivation to study the Latin language as a source of intellectual vocabulary and consolidation of knowledge acquired during group and individual work. In an experiment with first-year students of the Faculty of Clinical Psychology, a test was conducted to diagnose their motivation to learn. The experiment confirmed the sufficient validity of the technique. The result is that the number of students who successfully passed the exam was 87%.

In our opinion, the use of such practice-oriented tasks helps to get away from the monotony of textual materials and teach students to use a variety of Russian and foreign texts, containing professionally significant scientific and medical information in Latin. Practice-oriented tasks of an in-depth level, on our view, include writing the thesis of a speech or an essay on a topic that reveals certain aspects of the use of the Latin language in medicine and determined by the student, taking into account the recommendations of the teacher. These tasks are aimed at mastering the skills of reasoned presentation independent point of view and activate the independent cognitive activity of students in order to form the autonomy necessary in the conditions of continuous processes of education and self-education. Another component of career-oriented learning students of medical specialties learn Latin, which is significant in terms of a competency-based approach, are educational technologies. The modern process of teaching a foreign language focuses on the use of educational technologies that aimed at the rational distribution of time and

increasing the efficiency of educational activities. According to experts, these are modular and design technologies, as well as self-assessment technologies, the use of information resources Internet and modeling situations of professional communication. We believe that the implementation of these technologies contributes to transition to the competence-based paradigm in the professionally oriented teaching of students of medical specialties in the Latin language. Thus, modular technology provides differentiation of learning by allocation of modules, correlated with different aspects of the educational process and taking into account the heterogeneity of student groups. Design Technology contributes to the formation of students' autonomy, mastery of skills social interaction in the process of collective activity.

The method used in Latin classes is the “portfolio” method. With the help of the collected documents, it was possible to create an impression of yourself for a future employer. In the field of education, the portfolio method began to be used abroad. Currently, this method is actively used in higher education institutions. At the beginning of the academic year, 1st year students receive an assignment - when studying sections of the Latin language course, create their own documentary-type portfolio, answering in writing the questions given at the end of each lesson, thus drawing up a summary of the topic covered. In addition, students are invited to collect a portfolio of “works” that give an idea of the student’s educational and creative activity and the direction of his interests.

In conclusion we can see that the “portfolio” method involves the development of emotional and cognitive types of interest, independent activity skills, increasing student activity and motivation to study the Latin language. As follows from the data presented, the “round table” method contributes to the accumulation of material, its comprehension, the active assimilation of new things and the activation of what has been learned, the horizons broaden and the general cultural level rises. Some students were involved in assessment activities, which contributed to the intra-group integration of students and developed cooperation skills.

LITERATURE:

1. Bespalko V.P. Components of pedagogical technology. M.: "Pedagogy"; 1989.
2. Guzeev V.V. Pedagogical technology in the context of educational technology. M.: Public education; 2001.
3. Selevko G.K. Modern educational technologies: textbook. M.: Public education; 1998.
4. Khmel N.D. Theory and technology of implementing a holistic pedagogical process: a textbook. Almaty: ASU named after. Abaya; 2002.
5. Kalmurzaevna, U. A. (2023). The Effectiveness of Modern Methods in Teaching Foreign Languages.
6. Kalmurzaevna, U. A. (2022). The Use of Innovative Technologies in Increasing the Efficiency of English Teaching.
7. Kalmurzaevna, U. A. (2022). Effective Use of Modern Innovative Technologies in Teaching English.
8. Kalmurzaevna, U. A. (2022). INGLIZ-TILINI O'QITISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH.
9. Utambetova, A. (2022). LINGUOCULTURAL PROBLEMS IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE (Doctoral dissertation, Uzbekistan, Tashkent).
10. Esonovna, A. S. (2020). Linguistic features of Latin and Greek synonymous morphemes in the lexical system of the french language. International scientific review, (LXXII), 47-48.
11. Esonovna, A. S. (2023). Substitution of Latin and Greek Morphemes in Words in Medical Terminology. Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science, 4(2), 32-34.
12. Ziyoda, A., Mukaddam, S., & Shakhnoza, A. (2019). Communicative peculiarities of impersonal sentences in English discourse. Вопросы науки и образования, (7 (53)), 82-84.
13. Esonovna, A. S. (2023). LOTIN VA YUNON TILLARINING TIBBIYOT TERMINOLOGIYASIDAGI O 'RNI.

14. Abrayeva, S. E., Esanov, U. J., Saydullayeva, M. A., & Shirinkulova, S. M. (2022). Linguistic Features of Latin and Greek Synonymous Morphemes in the Lexical System of the French Language (Based on Medical Texts).